

Review Article

Seizing the Moment and Living to the Fullest

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Abstract: The review is based on the book, “The Last Lecture,” co-written by Randy Pausch and Jeffery Zaslow. The former gave a lecture on, “Really Achieving Your Childhood Dreams” which was then realised into a book form. While Pausch had just a few months of good health left he was invited to give a “Last Lecture.” In an academic circle the senior professors in their late age are invited to give a last lecture. What legacy could they impart to the world? What wisdom could they give to the world to cherish? When Pausch was invited to give his Last Lecture he too was in such dilemma. He was dying within few months of time, he was leaving behind his wife, three children and his beloved friends. Would he only leave behind his loved ones or would he leave behind wisdom and legacy for the world? Can Pausch be a life-coach? Let us find out what legacy Pausch could leave behind for the world to remember him. It must be noted that the author has done justice in reviewing the book by considering the reviews written by others on the same book.

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What wisdom would we impart to the world if we knew it was our last chance? If we had to vanish tomorrow, what would we want as our legacy? (Pausch, & Zaslow 2018)

Introduction

It's a thing in academic circles to prepare a lecture and a common task for most university professors in their last year teaching to reflect on their experiences – or 'journeys'. Pondering the question – what wisdom would I impart to the world if it were my last chance? They invite a bunch of people (colleagues, students and friends) to come and see it. An impending death has a way of focusing your attention on what is truly important (Bogue, 2019). They consider the end of their life time and to ruminate on what really matters most to them and lecture about it to the audience. One of such incidents took place in the life of Professor Randy Pausch who was dying of pancreatic cancer. He gave a talk on the "Last Lecture" at the Carnegie Mellon University, Pittsburgh (USA) where he was a professor of computer science for so many years.

During the "Last Lecture" most people in the audience expect the lecture to be about demise and the life lesson that the lecturer had learned while he lived. However, Pausch had a different story to tell. His lecture was unlike the conventional last lectures. Instead, he lectured about life and how to achieve one's childhood dreams. He has been the epitome of making these dreams to come true. Randy Pausch has combined the humour, inspiration, and intelligence that made his lecture such a phenomenon and given it an indelible for mark form. He had such a profound appreciation for life despite of knowing that he had just few months to live. But the lecture he gave, 'Really

Achieving Your Childhood Dreams’, was not about dying. It was about the importance of overcoming obstacles, of enabling the dreams of others, of seizing every moment (because time is all you have and you may find one day that you have less than you think). It was a summation of everything Randy had come to believe. It was about living.

What is the “Last Lecture” all About?

The *Last Lecture* is a book co-written by computer science professor Randy Pausch and *Wall Street Journal* reporter Jeffrey Zaslow and was published in 2008 by Hyperion. It is based on the highly acclaimed and inspirational lecture presented by Randy Pausch himself at Carnegie Mellon University, where he taught, on September 18, 2007 (eNotes, 2020).

Randy Pausch has been recently diagnosed with a terminal illness and he just has few months to live, could his “Last Lecture” be on death, or on the regrets of life? Or could it be a remorseful talk on, “Could have been..., what if..., I wish...?” Audience could have expected his lecture to be on death or something he regretted not doing it.

Using the forum of his university’s “Last Lecture” series, the terminally ill Pausch decided to distill his life lessons into a talk for students, friends and colleagues about how to achieve one’s childhood dreams. When Jeffrey Zaslow the columnist of “Wall Street Journal” wrote a column about the lecture, and a video of the speech was posted on the Internet, the reaction was overwhelming. Thereafter, to adapt the lecture into a book, Pausch dictated his thoughts to Zaslow while on his daily bike rides determined to maintain his fitness and minimize his time away from his family during the final months of his life. (Larson, 2008)

Pausch’s was dying, leaving behind his wife and three children along with his dear friends. It could have been his saddest lecture on death. But Pausch gives a twist in the story. Let us put ourselves in his shoe for some time before we really talk about this present

book. Just imagine like Pausch if you knew you had a few months of good health, how would you like to spend your time? Would you spend your short time that is left for you with your family, with your loved ones? Would spend time giving all the lectures to your children you could have given the next twenty years on how to live life? Would you pursue to achieve your childhood dreams before you die? Or would you spend the time sorrowing for not having much time left for you to live? But he knew feeling sorry for his plight could do him no good thus regarding his situation he described as, “While I could easily feel sorry for myself, that wouldn’t do them, or me, any good.” (Pausch, 2008) Randy Pausch, a computer science professor at Carnegie Mellon University, who has been diagnosed with terminal pancreatic cancer was in such dilemma. He was asked to give a “Last Lecture” and he could not imagine it to be his last one. He said, “We cannot change the cards we are dealt, just how we play the hand.” In such a pathetic situation anyone could have been disheartened. But Pausch was not so, he was a different person totally having a positive outlook toward life. He was in his own words, “An injured lion still wants to roar.” (Pausch, 2008)

The book Last Lecture is a longer version of the lecture professor Pausch gave at Carnegie Mellon University (CMU) before he lost his battle to pancreatic cancer, entitled “Really Achieving Your Childhood Dreams.” The book focuses on the core principles for his children to embody as part of their everyday lives, this book highlights the importance of mentors, appreciating life, accepting the things you cannot change, striving towards achieving one’s childhood dream, and about the importance of overcoming obstacles, of enabling the dreams of others, of seizing every moment. (SeeKen 2019)

Written with humour and wisdom, this book serves as a reflection of the main points of Pausch’s lecture. In it, Pausch discusses the importance of childhood dreams and how to go

about achieving them as one grows older. The major points of his book include taking the time to dream, the importance of good parents in a child's life, and how to put people before materials. Intertwined in the major themes of his lecture are Pausch's own personal anecdotes, complete with how he was able to turn his boyhood dreams into reality, including becoming an Imagineer for Walt Disney World, and creating the Alice software project.

In *The Last Lecture*, through his stories and experience, Pausch imparts readers with a "how-to" guide when striving to reach goals and dreams, but the book also serves as one man's legacy to his three young children. Pausch lived to see *The Last Lecture* become a *New York Times* best seller in April of 2008. He lost his battle with pancreatic cancer on July 25, 2008, at the age of forty-seven, but not before inspiring millions of readers to never stop believing in their dreams. Pausch's original lecture was titled "Really Achieving Your Childhood Dreams" and was directed at young adults. He stresses the importance of taking the time to dream and of having parents who encourage creativity, emotion, and intellectual exploration. (Larson May 2008)

He finds himself winning the parent lottery. He was influenced by his loving and supporting parents. During his life, he learnt many lessons from his experiences and has shared them in a striking manner. He also reveals how he achieved his childhood dream of becoming a Disney Imagineer, getting to Zero Gravity, being the coolest guy at amusement park and playing in the National Football League (which he never made it).

This book is inspiring, motivating and can craft the inanimate to life. The author has beautifully combined humour, intelligence, and wisdom. He has exemplified many stories which cover subjects like hard work, team work, sacrifice, self-confidence, modesty, dreaming big, perseverance, positivity, courage and dealing with adversity. For the reader, the book is a glimpse into the life of a

dying man who fights every moment to be alive and not a mere story. (Rishabh, 2018)

On the last page, he closes with the following poignant statement: “My life will be lost to pancreatic cancer. Two organizations I have worked with that are dedicated to fighting this disease are: The Pancreatic Cancer Action Network and The Lustgarten Foundation.” (Pausch, 2008) This book makes us feel like family to him, supporting him in his battle against a terminal cancer. “time is all you have” He said, “and you may find one day that you have less than you think you do” (Pausch, & Zaslow 2018). In short, it was about living one’s life. He managed to motivate his audience even with his failures and adventures.

My Reflection on the Book, “Last Lecture”

His second sentence in the ‘*Introduction*’ to the book is, “I have only a few months left to live.” When one reads such an opening line one expects the book to be of demise or of regrets. But that is not what the book is all about. It is far from being the book on sadness, demise or regrets. It is rather about life, achieving one’s childhood dreams and helping others to achieve their dreams.

Although he has just a few months to live, he is full of life. As we read through the book, we realise he has such an optimistic outlook to life. While anybody who has just few months to live could have been discouraged, worried or be intimidated by death, he is not in denial of death he cannot dismiss death, he would happily embrace his end. In a few months’ time he will be gone forever leaving behind his, most beloved – wife, children and dear ones. But the thought of dying soon could never let him down. Instead, he is living his life to the brim and he cannot think of living life without having fun. He opines, “I don’t how not to have fun. I am dying and I am having fun. And I am going

to keep having fun every day I have left.” He takes pleasure in every small moment of life. He mentions the joy he felt when spending time with his children. He remembers sitting down to watch a movie on New Year’s Eve when his wife’s waters broke. He describes his tears of joy when realising a job as a Disney Imagineer, for few even get to envisage such dreams and much less have the opportunity to live them. (Pausch, 2008)

Written in a highly personable and conversational fashion, *The Last Lecture* is part of autobiography, part life lesson, coming straight from the heart.

Written in a highly personable and conversational fashion, *The Last Lecture* is part of autobiography, part life lesson, coming straight from the heart. This inspiring catalogue of memories and musings is both powerful and raw. Pausch recounts life stories, illustrating wide ranging themes like hard work, determination, sacrifice, conviction, dreaming, bravery, hardship and misfortune, as we have discussed before. This book is divided into six chapters. The first chapter deals with, *The Last Lecture*, followed by; *Really Achieving Your Childhood Dream*, *Adventures . . . and Lessons Learned*, *Enabling the Dreams of Others*, *It’s About How to Live Your Life* and the *Final Remarks* of which every chapter is dealt in depth.

The first chapter is a background on the last lecture at Carnegie Mellon, the second chapter on how he really did achieve his childhood dreams some of them like; being in Zero Gravity, Being Captain Kirk, Authoring the article in the world book encyclopaedia, etc., the third chapter is about how we out to help each other in achieving goals, how to help others achieve their goals and importance of having an encouraging parents, the fourth chapter is deals Randy lists the rules by which he tried to live his life, and the final remarks is a summation of the book. Each chapter brings a new dimension to Pausch’s character and as the book progresses you

begin to feel you are getting to know the auto-biographer. So, this book is also likened to that of a memoir.

Randy's view of "failures" is that it is what gives us experience. He even had an award for "glorious failure" in his "building virtual worlds" course. He rightly puts it, "*Experience is what you get when you didn't get what you wanted*" For instance, one of his childhood dreams was to be play in the National football League (NFL), but sadly he never made it there. Though he did not make it to playing in National football League, he did learn a great lesson from the football coach himself.

"When you see yourself doing something badly and nobody's bothering to tell you anymore, that's a bad place to be. You may not want to hear it, but your critics are often the ones telling you they still love you and care about you, and want to make you better."

"Fear turned to awe when I met my coach, Jim Graham" (Pausch, & Zaslow 2018). In his lecture he mentions how they were taught life lessons as they were taught how to play football. "*Fundamentals. That was a great gift Coach Graham gave us. Fundamentals, fundamentals, fundamentals. As a college professor, I've seen this as one lesson so many kids ignore, always to their detriment: You've got to get the fundamentals down, because otherwise the fancy stuff is not going to work...* (and) '*When you're screwing up and nobody says anything to you anymore, that means they've given up on you*' *That lesson has stuck with me my whole life. When you see yourself doing something badly and nobody's bothering to tell you anymore, that's a bad place to be. You may not want to hear it, but your critics are often the ones telling you they still love you and care about you, and want to make you better"* (Pausch, & Zaslow 2018). The life lesson he learned during his training he

could never forget and they he cannot but pass it on to the generations to come. (Jayson, 2012)

The book also explores his gratitude for his upbringing by beloved parents, to his time spent with his own wife and kids. Pausch had many experiences and learned lessons from all of them. He equates his time of playing football to the understanding of the importance of teamwork and striving through adversity; whilst experiencing sacrifice and modesty the day that he found his late-father's war medals – something he knew nothing about.

In a chapter entitled, "*It's About How You Live Your Life*," Pausch opens up about living with cancer and how it might affect his life. Even with the knowledge of his ailment, Pausch maintains a constant positive outlook to life. He gives himself permission to keep dreaming and achieving, pointing out with poignant honesty that we have a finite amount of time on this planet and time spent complaining is time that takes us away from achieving our goals. He is ready to die because he feels he has lived life without regrets. He loved dearly his wife and children, he kept the rapport with his friends and colleagues and he achieved most of his childhood dreams. Nothing does he have in life to regret about. (Sweetnam, 2018)

Just about 200 pages, "The Last Lecture" is a small book. In every page you will find a man's agony in knowing that soon his children will not have a father to protect and guide them. Randy writes in such an honest and passionate way that you will find it hard to stop once you start reading the book. He will leave his wife a widow and his children, orphans. Leaving them behind and dying is sad thing but when you are sure that it is going to happen in a few months' time, it is the saddest thing. The book concludes with Pausch's dreams for the future, and those that he has for his family. He gives thanks to his Wife, Jai as his caregiver and on the last page of his deeply meaningful memoir he concludes; '*The talk wasn't just for those in the room. "It was for my kids."*

A Critical Analysis on the Book

When you read the book, it feels as if you are going through the entire life of Randy in a few minutes. We learn how he achieved his childhood dreams even when there are some really hard obstacles. According to him, the obstacles are there for a reason, it is to keep the “other” people out! As he said, *“The brick walls are there for a reason. The brick walls are not*

there for a reason. The brick walls are not there to keep us out; the brick walls are there to give us a chance to show how badly we want something”

there to keep us out; the brick walls are there to give us a chance to show how badly we want something” It still rings in my ears and I feel like his lecture is an advice directed to me. Most of his advice on life is actually ancient wisdom and clearly these are all principles valid till the end of humanity (importance of hard work, dreaming big, showing gratitude etc.). It is interesting to see them in the context of Randy’s life. If you are looking for any sort of deep philosophical discussions, this is not the book best suiting but if you are looking for an inspiration and advice on how to dream big, how to live life to the fullest even when we know our life is short, then this book is *par excellence* for that matter.

Randy’s message, *“It’s not about how to achieve your dreams, it’s about how to lead your life, if you lead your life the right way, the karma will take care of itself, the dreams will come to you,”* (Pausch, & Zaslow 2018) according to me is a universal message. It is not only about a dreaming and achieving one’s own childhood dreams but he advises us on how to live a life of integrity and honesty. His advice is powerful and awe-inspiring. *“If I only had three words of advice, they would be, Tell the Truth. If got three more words, I’d add, all the time.”* (Pausch, 2008) It is certainly admirable that Randy manages to

rise above his circumstances and to continue to be a teacher even unto his death. As the author himself has shared, the book is not about dying but about living. I do know for sure that it has provided me with lots of food for thought about what I should do with my own life. Reading this gives me strength.

Conclusion

Through his life, Randy demonstrated how sheer hard work and perseverance could help one to realise one's dreams regardless of one's station in life. He also acknowledges the vital importance of how others can help make all the difference – from his dad, his wife Jai, his three young kids, to his former mentors Professor Andy van Dam, and Coach Graham. Though the book is titled as “The Last Lecture,” it is a written version of the talk he gave on, “Really Achieving Your Childhood Dreams.” As one reads through the book, the *Last Lecture*, one realises that the book is not about dying but about living- seizing the moment and living life to the fullest. Through this book Randy leaves behind a legacy that would benefit humanity.

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